

FORMATION OF STUDENTS ' TALENT IN THE PROCESS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION

Kattakulova Nozbibi Shokir kizi

kattaqulovanozbibi@gmail.com.

+998940721522

TerSPI 2nd year graduate in the specialty theory and methodology of
Education and training (Primary Education)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854303>

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilar iqtidorini shakllantirish to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: shaxs, tarbiya, ilm, iqtidor, motiv, pedagogik texnologiya, idrok, tafakkur, muhit, oila, maktab, mahalla

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о формировании талантов учащихся в процессе начального образования.

Ключевые слова: Личность, образование, наука, талант, мотивация, педагогическая технология, восприятие, мышление, среда, семья, школа, соседство.

Annotation: This article provides information on the formation of students' talents in the process of primary education.

Keywords: personality, education, science, talent, motivation, pedagogical technology, perception, thinking, environment, family, school, neighborhood

Advanced pedagogical technology is based on the principle of "Teacher - Education - student" in which the student becomes a subject, that is, an active participant in the educational process, creating conditions for his search, observation.

In this, the curriculum and textbook should be the direct organizer of this process, and the teacher should skillfully and perceptively control this complex process.

In order to achieve full fulfillment by all students of the requirements established in the state educational standards of general secondary education, to increase the effectiveness of education, it is necessary to seek new pedagogical technologies (application), create innovations and introduce them into practice. Humanity develops through the production of material goods, knowledge of the laws that apply in Nature, Society and human thought, and the teaching of knowledge about the material and spiritual world to young people. Failure to attach sufficient importance to these processes, ignoring any of them, leads society to a crisis. The production of material goods is a universal experience, which is aimed at creating the economic basis of society. The Economic Sciences study the laws, principles, methods of production. The phenomena of Nature, Society and thinking are studied by philosophy, natural and Social Sciences. The knowledge gained in these disciplines serves for humanity itself. After all, by using the accumulated knowledge in practice, humanity protects itself from natural whims - hunger, cold, disasters, as well as economic and political decline. The content of the information reflects the general basis of the culture, production and thinking of modern science, techniques. Consequently, in the content of information, leading views on science, technology, culture, production, thinking, ideas, theories, facts are given, views, ideas, theories, links between facts are considered information logic. Information theory is engaged

in the issues of the preparation of children, the selection of information logic in accordance with age characteristics and their pedagogical processing. In later years, there has been a growing tendency to approach the content of information systematically. M.N.Skatkin, V.V.Kraevsky, I.Ya.Katorese scientists, such as Lerner, have proven in their scientific research that the content of information consists of the following four elements:

-
knowledge system. Knowledge is the materialized appearance of laws that apply in nature, in society, in the human mind, through the means of various signs (for example, writing). Knowledge can be seen, idea, definition, rule, precision, axiom, theorem, fact, etc. is given in the form;

- skills and competencies - are formed by ways of mastering knowledge, applying acquired knowledge to various educational conditions. The lower stage of qualification is called skill. Through exercise, training (exactly repetition without changing the same activity), the skill turns into a higher stage-qualification. Qualification is an automated skill.

When the issue of giftedness is approached psychologically, giftedness is associated with the experience of creative activity, which means going beyond the limits of thinking and activity that has become a tradition. With ways to master new ways of functioning, to solve educational and life problems in original ways, to set tasks for oneself, students acquire the experience of creative activity;

- relationship system. The attitude to Nature, Society, thinking is the next component of the content of information. As the student assimilates one or another educational material, he also revives the activities of the generations who lived before in his career. Appropriation is the incorporation of the result of one's own activities into the result of others' activities. Mastering is a psychological phenomenon and consists of the following components.

Perception. What is studied - the reflection-perception of the essence of the host in the mind - is referred to as perception. It is a broad concept that also encompasses experiences involving sensory organs (knowledge of objects hised using readings such as sight, hearing, visions of what happened before the experience-phenomena, familiar and isolated of thing-phenomena. The task of the teacher is to ensure the active perception of the educational material of children, to arouse various motives (desire, passion, interest), to participate in education most of the sensory organs, depending on the possibility.

Understand. The Advanced Higher form of perception is understanding. What is being studied is the fascination of the composition of the phenomenon, the relationship between them, the analysis of connections, the separation of the main and secondary signs of concepts, the knowledge of the structural elements of the educational material and the connections between them, the knowledge perceived by ways of understanding causal connections goes up to the level of understanding.

Thinking. Thinking about the features of educational material, comparing things and phenomena, distinguishing their features, the task set, children's thinking with ways to solve problems are organized. Thinking about understood educational materials ensures a higher level of acquired knowledge. Independent work, the application of training assignments to education, the omission of problems and questions increase the effectiveness of the thinking process.

Generalization. The highest level of assimilation is generalization, which applies in the forms of separation of the main features of the educational material and, conversely, addition,

embedding knowledge into one system, application of the learned knowledge to new educational conditions. The creative organization of the educational process on a scientific basis is the basis of individual perfection. Educating the maturing youth through education, they instill in their minds humanity, nationalism and patriotism. Any activity carried out consciously and conscientiously positively affects the personality of the child. The scientifically based process of education and upbringing forms the initial buds of creativity, forming a social character in the child.

And the creative content of the attitude to science, to the craft, instills in the person of the child a high awareness and conscientious duty, which creates an internal, spiritual preparation in the child in order to work towards the happiness of the nation.

Even at primary school age, there is a period when the child has fully formed as a person, and all his actions are within the framework of imitation. To make these qualities positive in the process of primary education, a jeweler needs a delicate, timely extremely scientific approach. Otherwise, the Sprout, which has not yet formed, will initially be much more inclined to work for itself within the framework of its own personal motives, to value its own labor and look at the work of others with disregard.

Working with elementary school students is a scientific activity that requires incredibly skill, creativity, initiative and, moreover, patience. In the process of organizing this activity, first of all, it is necessary to know in depth the specific spiritual world of each child, the buds of talent and be able to correctly determine the corresponding educational process. These factors form the basis of the complex of factors of the human environment and upbringing (IMT - factor). Because, in order to achieve quality and effectiveness in education, factors affecting the quality of Education (TSTEO) require the use and organization of tools affecting the quality of Education (TSTEVS) on a scientific and creative basis.

In the complex of IMT - factors, the environmental factor requires special attention. Family, School, neighborhood, Media (Media), etc. the environment that depends on the life of the child gradually begins to form its influence in the minds of the elementary school student.

All this is something new for the child. This thing that the environment presents, the reader's thinking is powerless to logically analyze and select phenomena. By itself, this situation stifles Independence, hard work, initiative, the development of such qualities as patriotism and honesty in the person of the child, which have not yet formed. Increasing excessive control over student activities, excessive torture, Coercion, among others, also do not do well in the educational process, but have an extremely negative effect on the psyche.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Qarori PQ-4306-son 03.05.2019. Iqtidorli yoshlarni aniqlash va yuqori malakali kadrlar tayyorlashning uzluksiz tizimini tashkil etish chora-tadbirlari.

Iqtidorli o'quvchilar bilan ishlash tizimini takomillashtirish maqsadida 2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yil 27- iyundagi "Yoshlar- keljagimiz" Davlat dasturi to'g'risida"gi PF-5466-son farmoni.

3. 2018-yil 14-avgustdagi "Yoshlarni ma'naviy- axloqiy va jismoniy barkamol etib tarbiyalash, ularga ta'lim-tarbiya berish tizimini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga ko'tarish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-3907-son Qarori.

4.Rahmatova F.G'. "Iqtidorli o'quvchilar bilan ishlash texnologiyasini takomillashtirish haqida" monografiya. Samarqand 2020

5.www.hozir.org

6.<https://arxiv.uz>

